

CONCEPT AND MANAGEMENT OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE IN UNANI SYSTEM OF MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease is an age-related chronic progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by disturbance of multiple cortical functions, including memory, orientation, judgement comprehension, language and learning capacity. More than 25 million people in the world are currently affected by Alzheimer's disease with around 5 million new cases occurring every year. In the Unani system of medicine there is no direct reference to this disorder but Alzheimer's disease is almost associated with *Nisyan* or *fasad-e-takhayyu'l* or *dimagh ki kharabi*. It is due to viscid phlegm (*Balgam Ghaleez*) and excess moistness (*Rutoobath*) in brain. The signs and symptoms of *nisyan* are *butlan-e-takallum* (speech impairment), *butlan-e-tahrir* (writing impairment), and *fasad-e-fikr* (impaired thought), which worsen gradually with time. Unani system of medicine is endeavored with enormous single and compound drugs with least side effects which can enhance the condition. This review paper will reveal the concept,

etiopathology, sign & symptoms, preventive measure and management.

KEYWORDS: Alzheimer's disease, Unani Medicine, *Nisyān*, *fasad-e-takhayyu'l*.

INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's Disease is a neurodegenerative disorder of the brain, which is the most common and aggressive form of dementia, manifesting in memory, language, and behavioral deficits. More than 25 million people in the world today are affected by dementia, most suffering from Alzheimer's Disease.^[1] Worldwide, the global prevalence of dementia was estimated to be 3.9 % in people aged 60+ years, with the regional prevalence being 1.6 % in Africa, 4.0 % in China and Western Pacific regions, 4.6 % in Latin America, 5.4 % in Western Europe, and 6.4 % in North America. More than 25 million people in the world are currently affected by dementia, most suffering from AD, with around 5 million new cases occurring every year. The number of people with dementia is anticipated to double every 20 years.^[2]

In Unani classic literature, this disease is not mentioned by its name, Alzheimer's, because this disease was named in the 20th century after German psychiatrist and pathologist Alois Alzheimer, who first described it in 1906.^[3,4] since this disorder is almost always associated with or *fasaad-e-zikr* and *Nisyān* (amnesia) and both conditions are characterized by impairment or loss of memory. The signs and symptoms of *Nisyān* (amnesia) are *Buṭlān al-Takallum* (speech impairment), *Buṭlān al-tahrir* (writing impairment), and *Fasād al-Fikr* (impaired thought), which worsen gradually with time. Inability to describe dream headache, giddiness, discharge of fluid from the mouth and nose, excessive sleepiness, and difficulty in speech are also mentioned as symptoms of *Nisyān* (amnesia).^[5] The eminent Unani physicians *Abu Bakr Mohammad bin Zakariya Razi*, *Ali Ibn Abbas Majoosi*, *Ibn e Sina*, *Ibn e Hubal Baghdadi*, etc., have mentioned the basic concept of this disorder as well as symptoms and signs which are similar to Alzheimer's Disease.

Etiopathology

The cause of Alzheimer's Disease is poorly understood. It is believed to occur when abnormal amounts of amyloid beta accumulate extracellularly as amyloid plaques and tau proteins or intracellularly as neurofibrillary tangles form in the brain, affecting neuronal functioning and connectivity, resulting in a progressive loss of brain function.^[6] It is a multifactorial disease in which the older age is strongest risk factor, there are so many hypothetic risk factors associated with its slowly progression and development like Genetic hypothesis, Vascular pathway hypothesis, Psychosocial hypothesis etc. Early-onset familial Alzheimer's Disease is often caused by autosomal dominant mutations (e.g., mutations in

amyloid precursor protein, presenilin-1, and presenilin-2 genes), which account for only about 2% to 5% of all Alzheimer patients.^[7] Moderate to strong evidence from multidisciplinary research (epidemiologic, neuroimaging, and neuropathological studies) has emerged supporting the hypothesis that vascular risk factors (e.g, smoking, obesity, and high total cholesterol) and vascular morbidity (e.g, high blood pressure, diabetes, and silent brain infarcts and white matter lesions) are associated with an increased risk of Alzheimer's Disease.^[8] A systematic review found that psychosocial factors and actively integrated lifestyle over the lifespan may reduce the risk of Alzheimer's Disease. These factors include early-life high educational attainment, adult-life high work complexity, late-life rich social network, high levels of social engagement, and more frequently participating in physically and mentally stimulating activities.^[9-10] Occupational exposures to heavy metals such as aluminum and mercury have been suggested as a risk factor for Alzheimer's Disease, and even high consumption of aluminum from drinking water may be a risk factor for Alzheimer's Disease.^[11]

Whenever we review the ancient Unani literature, it is obvious that the Unani scholars have suggested that it is caused by **Balgham Lazij** (viscid phlegm). *Ali ibn e Abbas Majoosi* states that "loss or derangement in memory results from *Sū'-i-Mizāj Bārid Sāda* or *Sū'-i-Mizāj Bārid Māddī* of the anterior or posterior part of the brain."^[12]

Rabban Tabari narrates that in *Nisyān* (amnesia), there is an accumulation of *Balgham Lazij* (viscid phlegm) and moistness in the brain. Sometimes *Nisyān* (amnesia) is caused by being too *Yubūsat* (dryness) because the brain cannot remember due to excess *Yubūsat* (dryness), whereas the whole body gets *Bārid* (cold).^[13] *Abu bakr mohammad bin zakariya razi* states that "sometime the volume of brain is reduced in older people which affects the cognitive function of the brain."^[14]

Zakariya Razi further states about *Buṭlān-i-Dhikr* (loss of memory) that this happens with the excess of *Burūdat* (coldness) and *Ruṭūbāt* (wetness) in the brain, which makes the brain so cold that it prohibits absorption of things. The condition of the brain is like melted wax, which does not take the impression of a stamp. In some people, excess dryness results in *Buṭlān-i-Dhikr* (loss of memory), which does not protect memory. The brain becomes like hard wax, which does not take the impression of a stamp.^[15]

Signs, symptoms and classification

Early symptoms of Alzheimer disease can comprises on difficulty performing tasks that take some thought, but used to come easily, such as balancing a checkbook, playing complex games (bridge), and learning new information or routines, getting lost on familiar routes, language problems, such as trouble remembering the names of familiar objects, losing interest in things previously enjoyed and being in a flat mood, misplacing items, personality changes and loss of social skills, mood changes leading to aggressive behavior, poor performance of job duties. As Alzheimer disease becomes worse, symptoms are more obvious and interfere with the at night, , delusions, depression, and agitation, difficulty doing basic tasks, such as preparing meals, choosing proper clothing, and driving, difficulty reading or writing, forgetting details about current events, forgetting events in one's life history and losing self-awareness, hallucinations, arguments, striking out, and violent behavior, Poor judgment and loss of ability to recognize danger, using the wrong word, mispronouncing words, or speaking in confusing sentences, withdrawing from social contact.^[16]

On the basis of etiology, this disease has been classified into two types.

1. Due to excess *Burūdat* (coldness) and *Ruṭūbāt* (wetness) of posterior brain region.

In this type patient sleeps excessively, if he is addressed at a particular time, he understand the sentence, but if he is asked to recall it after a while, he cannot do so. There will be nasal discharge, discomfort in posterior part of head and difficulty in the climbing down the stairs.

2. Due to excess *Burūdat* (coldness) and *Yubūsat* (dryness) of posterior brain region.

In this type the patient will suffer from chronic insomnia, dryness of nostrils and difficulty in talking rapidly. In certain moments, the patient is able to remember things while they are present in front of his eyes and forgets as soon as they disappear. In case of excess *Burūdat* (coldness), he is not able to remember anything.^[17]

Hakeem mohd Azam Khan states about *Nisyān* (amnesia) in his book *Rumooz e azam* “*Nisyān* (amnesia) is name of that disease in which derangement of *Hāfiẓa* (memory), *Fikr* (thinking) and *Takhāyīl* (imagination) occur. Derangement of *Hāfiẓa* (memory) is that the patient forgets whatever he sees or hears. In derangement of *Fikr* (thinking), the patients have bad thoughts and his thinking power rate decline to zero. Derangement of *Takhāyīl* (imagination) is that whatever a patient feels and perceives is not retained and whatever he sees in dreams, he forgets. As a whole, its cause is the excess of coldness and moistness or coldness and dryness

which in cases of *Fasād al-Dhikr*, it occurs in posterior brain. In case of *Fasād al-Fikr*, it occurs in mid brain and in case of *Fasād al-Takhāyīl*, it occurs in anterior brain.^[18]

MANAGEMENT OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

Preventive Measures

Maintenance of six essential factors has special importance in Unani medicine for preservation of overall health condition. Walking in open air, stay in well ventilated houses, maintain proper personal hygiene, use properly washed and cooked eatables, use purified water to drink, do regular exercise and take adequate rest, maintain balance in *Nawm wa Yaqza* and *Ihtibās wa Istifrāgh*.

Ilaj bil ghiza

Dietary recommendations

Unani physicians have given detailed dietary recommendations for the management of AD. *Ghidhā' Laṭīf Kathīr al-Ghidhā' Jayyid al-Kaymūs, Ghidhā' Sarī'al-Nufūdh and Muqawwī Aghdhiya* are suitable for the patient of *Nisyān* (amnesia). Meat, soup, semiboiled eggs, *Mā' al-Jubn, Mā' al-Laḥm, Mā' al-'Asl, Panīr Māya, mazawwarat, hareera, sirka, khardal, khurfa, palak, kaddu*, nuts have been recommended.^[17]

Dietary restrictions

Aghdhiya Mubakkhira, Aghdhiya Mubarrida and cold water have been restricted.^[18]

Alcohol and use of *Piyāz* (*Allium cepa*, Linn.), *Kishnīz* (*Coriandrum sativum*, Linn.), *Bāqla* (*Phaseolus vulgaris*, Linn.), *Lobia* (*Vigna sinensis*), *Adas* (*Lens esculenta*, Moench), *Karnab* (*Brassica oleracea*), and *Krafs* (*Apium graveolens* Linn.) have been restricted for the patient of it.

USŪL-I 'ILĀJ (PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT)^[17,18]

Since dementia is caused by changes in the brain's temperament toward cold and moist or cold and dry states, the basic principles of treatment for *Nisyān* (amnesia) include.

- *Izāla-i Sabab* -To remove the causative factor.
- *Taskhīn* -To produce warmth.
- *Tajfīf* -To produce dryness when caused by *Rutūbat* (Moistness).
- *Ta'dīl-i Mizāj* - To normalize the temperament
- *Tanqia-i Dimāgh* -To Evacuate the Morbid Matter from the brain.
- *Taqwiyat-i Dimāgh* -To tone-up the brain

- *Tafrīh-i Taba* ‘-To produce exhilaration
- *Taskīn-i Waja* ‘ -To relieve pain.
- *Tanwīm* -To induce sleep

‘Ilāj bi’l-Tadbīr (Regimenal therapy)^[17-20]

1. *Fasd* (venesection) If the age, season and strength of the patient are favourable then *Fasd* (venesection) is advised.

2. *Huqna Mushila* (Purgative enema): The disease is commonly due to cold, moist and thick humour therefore evacuation/bio purification of the body is indicated by employing the procedure of *Huqna*(enema) and *Mus’hilat* (purgation).

3. *Natool* on the head, application of *Zimād*, *Naswar*, *Shamoom* are prescribed.

3 *Riyāzat* (exercise), *Dalk* (Massage) and *Mazmaza* (gargle) are also recommended.

4. According to a scientific report daily 20-30 minutes of brisk walking is very usefull in the *Nisyān* (amnesia). Efficacy of *Riyādat e khafeefa* 20 to 30 minutes of brisk walking speed of 4km /hour in the management of *Nisyān* (amnesia) was evaluated in 20 patient randomly assigned in to two groups. Group1 advised brisk walking daily for 30 minutes and Group 2 *recieved placebo.at the end of 6 month when two groups war compared result* showed that *Riyāzat e khafeefa* or brisk walking is useful in the *Nisyān* (amnesia).^[21]

5. Thought provoking activities, partying with friends, indulgence in entertaining activities, listening of music and use of aroma.^[4,19]

6. Regimenal therapies are prescribed for restoring the normal temperament of the brain.

7. The most promising treatments include lifestyle changes and medications. Studies show the following lifestyle changes may help improve behaviour in people with Alzheimer disease.

- *Riyāzat* (exercise): A regular walk with a caregiver or trusted companion may improve communication skills and reduce the chance of wandering.
- Calming music may reduce wandering and restlessness, boosts brain chemicals, and improves behavior.
- Relaxation training and other exercises that require focused attention may help boost social interaction and make it easier to do tasks.

‘Ilāj bi’l-Dawā’ (Pharmacotherapy)

Alzheimer's disease cannot be cured, however some patients may benefit from medications that reduce the illness course. Supplements, herbs, and lifestyle changes may also help lower

risk or enhance quality of life. In modern system of medicine Cholinesterase inhibitors (ChEI) therapy is presently regarded as the standard treatment of Alzheimer's disease. Four ChEIs drugs have been approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment of mild to moderate Alzheimer's disease. They are tacrine, donepezil, rivastigmine, and galantamine. These compounds increase the concentration of acetylcholine and the duration of its action in synapses by inhibiting the degradation of acetylcholine.^[22]

In Unani system of medicine treatment should be started with *Tanqiya'-i-Dimāgh* through the *Mundij* and *Mushil*. after that *Muḥāfiẓat*, *Muṣliḥat*, *Muqawwiyat*, *Mu'addilat*, *Mūnaish i-Harārat Gharīziyya* are used as memory enhancer and strengthening of *Quwā. Mā' al-Usūl* is recommended in the first step of ilaj of Alzheimer's disease patient.^[17] After that *Ayāraj-i Loghāziya*, 13.5 gm. along with decoction of *Halayla Siyāh* (*Terminalia chebula*, Retz.) 35 gm., *Mawīz Munaqqa* (*Vitis vinefera*, Linn.) 70 gm., *Aftīmūn* (*Cuscuta reflexa*, Roxb.) 40.5 gm., crushed *Reward* (*Rheum emodi*, Wall.) 10.5 gm. Shuld be given.

- Oral administration of powder of *Baram Dandī* (*Echinops echinatus*, DC.) in the dose of 12 gm with cow milk.
- Oral administration of powder of *Maghz-i Funduq* (*Corylus avellana*, Linn.) mixed with sugar.^[23]

Compound drugs^[23-25]

Zahbī 3gm. twice a day

Khamīra-i Zaharmuhra 6 gm. in the morning

Itrīfal-i Ustūkhudūs up to 12 gm.

Ma'jūn-i Nisyān 5 gm. in the morning.

UNANI MEDICINAL HERBS FOR MEMORY ENHANCEMENT

Adviya Mufradah (Single Drugs)^[26-36]

There are numerous single and compound drugs used for memory enhancement. single drugs include *Brhami* (*Bacopa monnieri*), *Waj* (*Acorus calmus*), *Kundur* (*Boswellia serrata*), *Zanjabīl* (*Zingiber officinale*, Roscoe.), *Khardal* (*Brassica nigra*), *Halayla Siyāh* (*Terminalia chebula*, Retz.), *Balela* (*Terminalia bellirica*), *Amla* (*Emblica officinalis*), *Haldi* (*Curcuma longa*), *Elva* (*Aloe vera*), *Qust* (*Saussurea lappa*), *Sa'ad ku'fi* (*Cyperus rotundus*), *Sumbul-al-Ṭīb* (*Nardostachys jatamansi* (D.Don) DC.), *Kabāb Chīnī* (*Piper cubeba*), *Dār Filfil* (*Piper longum* L.), *Āqarqarḥā* (*Anacyclus pyrethrum*), *Gilo* (*Tinospora cordifolia*),

Khūlanjān (*Alpinia galangal*), *Asgand* (*Withania somnifera*), *Uṣṭūkhūdūs* (*Lavandula stoechas*), *Balādur* (*Semecarpus anacardium*), *Darchini* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*), *Ood Saleeb* (*Paonea officinalis*), *Za'farān* (*Crocus sativus* L.), *Qaranful* (*Syzygium aromaticum* L.), *Pista* (*Pistacia vera*), *Tulsi* (*Ocimum basilicum*), *Asārūn* (*Asarum europaeum* L.), *Chilghoza* (*Pinus gerardiana* Wall. ex D.

Don), *Maghz-i-Bādām Shīrīn* (*Prunus amygdalus*).

Adviya Murakkabah (Compound drugs)^[18,20,24,26]

Compound drugs include

Majoon Barhami, *Majoon Bolas*, *Majoon Baladur*, *Majoon Waj*, *Majoon Falasafa*, *Majoon Kundur*, *Itriphala Sagheer*, *Itriphala Ustakhuddus*, *Jawarish Jalinoos*, *Majoon Najah*. *Majoon Hafiz al-Aql*, *Murabba Waj*, *Murabba Halela*, *Dawa al-Misk*, *Mufarreh Abresham*. *Mufarreh Halaylaji*.

SCIENTIFIC STUDIES ON ADVIYA NABATIYA FOR ALZHEIMERS DISEASE:

Za'farān (Crocus sativus Linn.)

It was demonstrated that saffron extract capsules administration significantly reduced cognitive decline when compared with memantine.^[37]

Brahmi (Centella asiatica)

In vitro, centella ethanol extract was found to improve neuronal viability, reduce neurotoxicity, and lower oxidative damage of β -amyloid aggregates. Centella water extract (CAW) treatment was found to improve learning, memory, and cognitive functions in aged mice.^[38]

Amla (Emblica officinalis)

Amla exhibited significant improvement in memory retention of young and aged rats in a dose-dependent manner. It reversed the diazepam and scopolamine induced amnesia. As a memory enhancer and reversal of memory deficits, *Emblica officinalis* plays an important role in the treatment of memory deficits and Alzheimer's Disease.^[39]

Kundur (Boswellia serrata Roxb.)

In a study conducted, it was revealed that the treatment of Alzheimer's disease induced rats with aqueous infusions of *B. serrata* at the dose of 45 and 90 mg/kg/day for 12 successive weeks significantly ameliorates the neurodegenerative characteristics in rats.^[40]

Hazrat Anus bin Malik (Radhi Allahu Anho) narrated, ‘Someone complained to Prophet (Salallahu Alaihe Wasallam) against his memory. He (Salallahu Alaihe Wasallam) said, take kundar (*Boswellia serrata*) and soak it in water and drink that water early in the morning. It is a useful phytotherapy for memory.^[41]

Sumbul al-Tib (Nardostachys jatamansi (D. Don) DC.)

In a study, *Nardostachys jatamansi* exhibited It boosts the antioxidant enzyme activities, prevents Tau-induced oxidative stress, ameliorates eye degeneration, and inhibits cholinesterase activities in Tau-induced Alzheimer’s Disease model. The current study investigates the neuroprotective properties of jatamansinol against Tau-induced neurotoxicity in the Alzheimer’s Disease model.^[42]

Kishnīz Khushk (Coriandrum sativum Linn.)

In a study conducted, *Coriandrum sativum* was given for 45 days for its efficacy on cognitive function in male *Wistar* rats. The study was conducted in comparison with aging, scopolamine and diazepam induced amnesia. It was concluded that *Coriandrum sativum* exhibited memory enhancing effects due to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and cholesterol.^[43]

Waj (Acorus calmus)

It is used as *Muqawwi-e-Bah* (Aphrodisiac), *Mufarreah* (exhilarant) and *Muqawwi-e-Hafiza* (memory improving).^[44,45] Recently, *Acorus calamus* has been reported to possess to high antioxidant activity.^[46]

Zanjabīl (Zingiber officinale Roscoe.)

According to a study conducted, it improves memory impairment induced by scopolamine via inhibition of acetylcholinesterase activity. As a booster of antioxidant and a reducer of free radical, *Zingiber officinale* plays an important role in the treatment of AD and memory deficits.^[47]

Zard Chob (Curcuma longa Linn.)

In Alzheimer’s disease, it has been shown that curcumin has the ability to inhibit A β oligomerization and fibril formation, enhance A β uptake by macrophages and inhibits the peroxidase activity of A beta-heme complex.^[48,49]

Asl al-Sūs (Glycyrrhiza glabra Linn.)

This plant belongs to the family of Fabaceae and it is used in the treatment of Alzheimer's disorder because of the presence of coumarins, isoflavonoids, saponins, flavonoids, and stilbenoids. Experimental results of the glycyrrhiza glabra plant extract administered orally to a 1-month-old albino rat for 6 weeks showed improved memory and learning capacity.^[50]

Gilo (Tinospora cordifolia Miers)

In vitro studies have suggested that *T. cordifolia* extracts and compounds can improve memory, cognition, and learning deteriorated by various neurodegenerative diseases. They also enhance the potential of the antioxidant system by restoring Glutathione (GSH) and Superoxide dismutase (SOD) levels and scavenging the free radicals that cause neuronal oxidative stress and neurodegeneration.^[51]

CONCLUSION

As the body's temperament turns BaridYabis with age, the brain's temperament also gets more Barid and its Quwat-e-Nafsaniyah decreases. Instead of baroodatwaratoobat, AD is caused by baroodatwayaboosat of the brain. Therefore, medications with a hot temperament are advised for AD. The Zakariya Razi states that in treatment, Kaifiyat-e-faila (active qualities, such as hotness and coldness) is more significant than Kaifiyat-e munfaila (passive qualities, such as wetness and dryness). Waj (Acoruscalmus), Barhami (Bacopa monnieri), Zaafran (Crocus sativus), Asgand (Withaniasomnifera), Ustukhuddus (Lavandula stoechas), Baladur (Semecarpusanacardium), OodSaleeb (Paonea officinalis), Qust (Saussurea lappa) *Fil-Fil Daraj* (Piper longum), Qaranfal (Syzygium aromaticum), Kabab Chini (Piper cubeba), Darchini (Cinnamomum zeylanicum), and Gingeber officinalis), and other single Unani medications with a hot temperament. The compound medications Jawarish Jalinoos, Majoon Barhami, Majoon Falsafa, Majoon Baladur, Majoon Najah, Murabba Waj, and Rohan Zaitoon, as well as Aqarqarha (Anacyclus pyrethrum), are more helpful in Alzheimer's disease. Hot *Mizaj* medications cause dryness in specific organs and parts of the body, according to a natural rule mentioned in Unani. This fact definitely takes into account that the dosage and length of therapies for AD should not cause more brain dryness, which could cause unwanted harm rather than healing.

The basic and essential idea of this ailment was well known to the Unani physicians. Additionally, they discussed the symptoms and indicators that are fairly comparable to those of Alzheimer's disease, and they were previously aware of the *Nisyān* (amnesia), including its

underlying causes, symptoms, complications, and management strategies. The Unani medical system has a unique method for treating Alzheimer's. The purpose of this review paper is to provide researchers with a fresh perspective on Alzheimer's disease. The veracity of this connection should be the primary focus of future research, according to scientists in this field. The mainstreaming of Unani medicine into the national and international healthcare systems is absolutely necessary.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest.

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